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IMPACT OF SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE ON PERFORMANCE AND JOB SATISFACTION: A STUDY ON SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to analyze spirituality at work and to discover how spirituality improves educator's performance and institutional effectiveness. Researchers have attempted to understand how spirituality benefits teachers and supports institutional performance while enhancing job satisfaction based on the existing literature. This paper introduces aspects of probable welfare and requirements of carrying spirituality into the workplace; providing suggestions for teachers to incorporate spirituality positively in institutions.

This research idea focuses on providing a critical review of the literature on workplace spirituality by examining the fundamental basis of the main trends among teachers at work.

Keywords- Spirituality, Work performance, Institutions, Human Resources, Teachers

Introduction:-

The resources of any Institution give optimum results only if they are utilized in an effective manner. Human resource is the most important asset and forms the intellectual capital of any set up. In the field of education teachers are among the most important factors who not only function as guides and facilitators for acquisition of knowledge but also as inculcators of values and transformers of inner being. The employee of any institution need to demonstrate that they can add value to the institution (Harari, 1993), thus to produce quality individuals we need quality teachers.

The economic upheavals have compelled people to rethink and bring a new perspective to workplace values through spirituality. The people have started promoting Cooperation rather than fear at the work place. (Labbs.J.J, 1995) Spirituality helps in instilling values and builds culture in an institution. (Jurkiewicz & Giacalone, 2004) High Spirituality makes employees more responsible and even loyal. (Rego & Cunha, 2008)

Spiritual Intelligence helps teachers to carry out their functions as teachers. Teachers are regarded as someone very high in society. (Emmon, 2000). Spiritual Intelligence helps teachers solve global problems as it creates global awareness. (Sisk, 2008)

UNESCO in 1996 said that "Education should contribute to every person's complete development –mind and body, Intelligence, sensitivity, aesthetics appreciation and spirituality"

Many institutions are now making effort to achieve success by using all its potential to maximize commitment, job satisfaction and internal motivation of employees through various spiritual domains (Mallik, Danish, & Ali, 2010).

People with higher level of spirituality have healthier, happier and more productive lives at work (Tischler, Biberman, & and Mckeage, 2002).

Spirituality is considered one of the key factors for the success of the educational institutions and ultimately for the professional life of the teachers.

In the present preview of modernization the quality of being spiritually intelligent is necessary for the teachers too. Teacher must have high spiritual intelligence which will be the highest guidance to them to carry out their functions as teachers with the highest regards and as noble as possible. The major role of a holistic educator is to awaken creativity and spiritual Intelligence of learners (Colalillo Kates, 2002).

It is important to make teachers spiritually intelligent as they can then enlighten and guide future educational reforms and policies in relation to both contents and methods for the holistic development of the individuals. Spiritual intelligence brings in teachers the ability to create meaning based on deep understanding and the positive attitude to solve problems. They are generally well satisfied with their workplace

(Vaughan,2002) gave three components of spiritual intelligence: - the ability to create meaning based on deep understanding of existential questions, an awareness of and the ability to use multiple levels of consciousness in problem solving, an awareness of the interconnection of all beings to each other and to the transcendent.

The major factor associated with school teacher's decision to leave or to remain in the teaching profession is their job satisfaction, Job satisfaction is related to working conditions and level of professionalism is a key factor in successfully recruiting and retaining teachers (Stanbury & Zimmerman, 2000). Job Satisfaction is "a pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job and an attitude toward one's job (Shahnawaz & Jafri, 2009). Teacher's job satisfaction refers to a teacher's affective relation to his or her teaching role and is the function of the perceived relationship between what one wants from teaching and what one perceives it is offering to a teacher (Zembylas & Papanastasiou, 2004).

(Dincer, 2009) Mentioned that spiritual intelligence provides a sense of personal wholeness, goal and direction, He pointed out teachers with high level of spiritual Intelligence are able to mould students from all age groups to experience a wholesome life filled with self-respect and creativity. Teachers with spiritual Intelligence are more satisfied with their jobs. Spiritual Intelligence has positive influence on Job Satisfaction (Cherati, Mahdavi, & Rezacian, 2013).

Objectives:-

- To examine whether spirituality increases teacher's well-being and quality of life.
- To understand teacher's sense of purpose and meaning at work with spirituality.
- To examine whether spirituality provides teachers a sense of interconnectedness with community.
- To provide suggestions for teachers for incorporating spirituality positively in schools.

Significance of the Study-

Few studies though are conducted on the relationship of spiritual Intelligence, performance and job satisfaction of the teachers but still the teaching profession in times of modernization needs more research work in this area so, a need was felt to study the spiritual Intelligence in relation to performance and job satisfaction of school teachers.

Review of Literature:-

Spirituality:

The term spirituality was first proposed by Stevens in 1996 and expanded by Emmons in 1999.

(Neck & Milliman, 1994) found that spirituality involves an individual's search to fulfill their potential for greater meaning and life purpose in their work, alongside a strong sense of community and need to contribute to the better of the society. Teachers must contribute in the development of the community as they have the ability to mould the personality of the students. (Amram, 2007) Spiritual intelligence was defined as ability to apply, manifest and embody spiritual resources, values and qualities to enhance daily functioning and wellbeing.

Spirituality as reported by many researchers is relatedness or connectedness to self, other's and higher power. It is often said that what one does on earth should be meaningful and beneficial to the individual, the institution, the community and mankind as a whole.

“Spiritual values are essential for people to excel and grow.”(Giacalone& Jurkiewicz, 2004). Spirituality helps in instilling values and builds culture in an institution. “Spiritual Values transcend knowledge and skills. Most researchers believe that spiritual intelligence is the experienced ability that allows individuals to achieve greater knowledge and understanding and provide background to achieve perfection and progress in life.

One who has internalized spiritual values will be more confident. The goal of spirituality is typically to reach a highly evolved personal state or attainment of one's highest potential which in turn can lead to greater creativity, motivation and institutional Commitment. Those who are guided by spiritual values are confident of their performance and this state of mind might provide added strength to handle multi-tasking.

Spirituality is concerned with unity, coherence and balance in both the individual and institutional life. It acknowledges the sacredness and connectedness to a divine source and to communities of people. Generally people have their own screening mechanism, using their spiritual values; they know whether what they are doing is ethical or unethical. This is where spiritual values help because they govern them.

“Spirituality helps employees to achieve Salvation through work.” Karakas reviewed about 140 articles on workplace spirituality and introduced:-Spirituality enhances employee's wellbeing and quality of life. b) Spirituality provides employees a sense of purpose and meaning at work and c) spirituality provides employees a sense of interconnectedness and community.

Workplace Spirituality helps employees achieve their goals without diminishing their creativity and helps them to deal with stressful work environment (Altaf.A & Awan, N.A, 2011). Workplace spirituality enhances workplace performance (Jurkiewicz, C.L & Giacalone, R.A 2004). Spirituality is an element of intelligence because it predicts functioning and adaptation and offers capabilities that enable people to solve problems and attain goals (Emmons.R, 2000)).

Zohar & Marshall (2000) defined spiritual intelligence as intelligence which people address and solve problem of meaning and value, place their actions and lives in a wider and richer meaning-giving context the intelligence with which people can assess that one course of action or one life path is more meaningful than other. (Amram & Dryer, 2007)) Have identified five construct of spiritual Intelligence; they are Consciousness, Transcendence, Grace, Meaning and Truth.

Teacher's Role (Commitment & Performance)

A teacher's role generally should include integration and application of knowledge and skills besides teaching. The integrity is prerequisite to personal success and for developing leadership skills. The people who have integrity build trust in their relations with other's they become valued as friends, colleagues, mentors and supervisors. They are respected and counted on to do what is right. They are able to balance respect and responsibility and they are able to share their values with others.

“A teacher means you show the way to other’s and you also think well about them and you want them to excel. Education should contribute to every person’s complete development- mind and body, Intelligence, sensitivity, aesthetics, appreciation and spirituality.” (UNESCO, 1996).

Many researchers through their observations have found that trust, creativity, honesty, sense of personal engagement, institutional commitment, job satisfaction, job involvement, job consciousness and motivational level of employees can be increased with the growth of spirituality in an institution.

Job Satisfaction:

An organization can conduct themselves fairly in a cooperative and responsible manner with a vision to foster charity and creativeness leading to higher productivity and accomplishment which can further supplement self-esteem of the employees so that they get the sense of job satisfaction.

The most important functions of spiritual intelligence in the workplace are to:-provide peace of mind, create mutual understanding and rapport between colleagues, increase job satisfaction and reduce job stress.

Job Satisfaction is a good feeling caused by appraising different aspects of one’s job. Similarly (Mottaz, 1998) defined job satisfaction as an emotional response to workplace condition appraisal. For measuring job satisfaction various dimensions have been developed by Stamps and Piedmont (1986) that are as follows: (1) Pay: refers to the amount of received money by employees, (2) Autonomy: refers to the independence and freedom in workplace, (3) Task requirements: refers to activities that should be done in a job, (4) Institutional policies: refers to managerial and institutional policies and procedures, (5) Interaction: refers to opportunities that employees are able to communicate with each other, (6) Professional status: refers to overall importance of a job perceived by an employee himself or by others.

(Nobi, Abdal, & Sajid, 2003)) Found female teachers enjoyed greater satisfaction than their male counterparts did. Married teachers showed more job satisfaction than unmarried teachers did. Teachers teaching in government schools showed more job satisfaction than teachers teaching in private schools. There was no significant change in the job satisfaction due to change in the level of independent variables like sex, marital status and types of schools, School Culture, teacher’s relationship with administration, working conditions and motivation were the factors which had a significant relationship with job satisfaction among school teachers. Male and female teachers are not different from each other on job satisfaction variable (Lal & Shergill, 2012).

Link between Spiritual Intelligence, Performance and Job Satisfaction:

Little attention has been paid to the link between spiritual intelligence, performance and job satisfaction (Rastgar, Davoudi, Oraji, & Abbasian, 2012) found that there is no significant relationship between Spiritual Intelligence and job satisfaction Whereas (Jelodar & Goodarzi, 2012) (Khorshidi & Ebadi, 2012) showed that there is significant positive relationship between these two variables .

Zohar & Marshall (2000) stated that when Spiritual Intelligence is high we appear to be intellectual and have proper behavior, However when spiritual intelligence is low people will appear to have problematic behavior They stated people with high Spiritual Intelligence demonstrated high measures of satisfaction and performance.

In a survey conducted in 1998 in America on 800 professionals it was asked if their spiritual lives were influenced by their positions. 33 percent responded that work was responsible for “greatly improving” their spirituality. It is significant to recognize that developing spirituality in a work setting is more about bringing out a quality that is already present and not about teaching something that is not there.

Teachers should be encouraged to talk about spiritual issues. Few things to observe would be: - Are teachers enthused by their work? What is the mission of the institution? What talents do teachers possess and how can the institution put them to meaningful use? Do they have spiritual balance and wellness?

Spirituality in workplace is characterized by the following traits:- a revival of the spirit of community in work, shared power, greater value for diversity , global stewardship, service-learning atmosphere, a recognition that human beings have a basic need for “relevance, recognition, meaning and self-transcendence .”

Research Methodology

This paper is based on information collected through interaction with school teachers and from personal observations. The secondary source of information is collected through various expert’s views and opinions.

Observations:- The future study in this area might help to prove that teachers with high spiritual quotient are better educators and are able to contribute more and result in formation of better community which in turn would lead to teachers taking most meaningful, uplifting and practical courses in life.

Implications:-

- a) **School Management:** It would help management to induct, train and retain good teachers and thus frame relevant HR policies. Institutions operating under new paradigm of spirituality would place emphasis on spiritual energy and flow, Shared vision and aligning employee-value with institutional values.
- b) **Teachers:-**The study would help teachers in adopting innovative teaching methods thus achieving salvation through work by which goal of the institution is also achieved As spirituality from institution point of view emphasizes on unity, coherence and balance in both the individual and institutional life and job satisfaction comes out of that
- c) **Students:-** The students’ holistic development would happen due to teachers adopting methods conducive to their overall development , As student’s progress is directly related to wellbeing of teachers, Its imperative to see that they are happy and contributing to the growth of the students positively
- d) **State Education Board:-** It would help the board to take into account spirituality as an important aspect and frame Refresher courses for teachers, where they try to impart training to bring awareness about the concept
- e) **Society/ Community:-** The study would help to bring change in the outlook by bringing stability in unstable world due to globalization and other factors , It would develop spiritual awareness for serving others as an expression of spiritual growth

Conclusion:- Though spirituality in the life of human beings is generations old, it is being revisited with lot of conviction and confidence. As Rigveda rightly says, “**Aano bhadraha Kratavo yantu vis wataha**” – Let noble thoughts come to us from every side. Honesty, Creativity, Reactiveness, Kindness, Dependability, Confidence and Courage, these internal values are interconnected to factors such as - Sense of purpose, High ethical standards, Acceptance, Peace, Trust, Respect, Understanding, Appreciation, Care, Involvement, Helpfulness. All the factors build team spirit and enhance performance which in turn fosters self-esteem of the employee and leads to job satisfaction.

People generally prefer to see a meaning and value in their life and work as well as are willing to make a difference to the life of others. Thus spirituality is the core that leads to ultimate level of intelligence without any religious bias and also helps to understand self in a better way.

Sogyal Rinpoche says in the Tibetan book of living and Dying “True spirituality is to be aware that if we are interdependent with everything and everyone else, even the smallest, least significant thought, word and action has real consequences throughout the universe. So, teachers as builders of community and nation require to be aware of their deeper nature and their conscious development requires them to value their deeper nature in taking next steps. The future must bring insights into past and new values.

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